

Criminal Exhibit the Feminine Violent Victim within Thai Newspaper

Authors : Supaporn Wimonchailerk

Abstract : This research aims to critical analyze the feminine violent within Thai daily newspaper. This study was qualitative base; content analysis from two popular newspapers (Thairath and Dailynews) two qualitative newspapers (Thaipost and Mathichon). Purposive sampling was used to select eleven specialize news reporters to do in-depth interview. The result found that, popular newspapers, Thairath and dailynews have presented feminine violent news in their paper more than Thaipost and Mathichon the qualitative newspaper. Beside, majority of sample present the feminine violent within news under the code of ethic, The National Press Council of Thailand. Interesting, the age of feminine violent victim was the information that has been focused most. The popular newspaper have illustrated crime scene photo on their first-page while qualitative newspaper used only headline to present the same news.

Keywords : ethic, feminine, journalism, newspaper, violent victim

Conference Title : ICEMBIT 2014 : International Conference on Economics, Management of Business, Innovation and Technology

Conference Location : London, United Kingdom

Conference Dates : June 29-30, 2014